

A Study of Chiral Mixed Ligand Metal Complexes and Enzymes as Catalysts in Resolution of 1,1'-Binaphthyl-2,2'-diol

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A variety of stereochemical investigations have been successfully conducted using optically active 2,2'-dihydroxy-1,1'-binaphthyls (binaphthols). Both the optical isomers (*R* and *S*) of the binaphthol can be converted into chiral catalysts for asymmetric catalysis¹ or into crown ethers², which are useful as stereoselective complexing agents. Earlier, classical methods were used to resolve the racemic binaphthols involving tedious separation of the diastereomeric derivatives³, or via chromatographic resolution upon an HPLC column packed with chiral stationary phase⁴. Recently, the diols have been resolved via enzymatic hydrolysis of racemic diesters⁵. We report here the resolution of racemic diester of 1,1'-binaphthyl-2,2'-diol (**1**) by enzymatic transesterification, instead of enzymatic hydrolysis, using methanol as solvent as well as a nucleophile. The enzymes can be replaced by the synthesised CMLM complexes as catalysts which can be modified further to get the product of better optical purity.

Results and Discussion

The diacetate of 1,1'-binaphthyl-2,2'-diol (**1**) was transesterified with methanol as a nucleophile as well as solvent in presence of CMLM complexes as well as lipases as catalysts to get the product **1** of varying optical purity. The results (Table 1) indicate that the percentage enantiomeric excess (*ee*%) of the product increases on proceeding down the Table from catalyst **a** to catalyst **d** with the increase in steric bulk on the chiral ligand *L'*. The significance of the steric factor

in the chiral ligand for enantioselectivity capability of the catalyst is clearly observed. Activity of the catalyst in general depends upon its interactions with the substrates. The dependence of intensity of this metal-to-substrate interaction upon their hydrogen-bonding capability, steric hindrance, and on dipolar and charge transfer interactions is well known⁶. Applying the same logic, catalysts **a** and **d** were modified by replacing the amino acids by their respective *N*-benzoyl derivatives to get catalysts **e** and **f** respectively. The results suggest that the above mentioned interactions were in reality improved, as expected, by introduction of additional keto group and phenyl ring in the ligand *L'* of the modified catalysts. Thus catalysts **e** and **f** yielded products with better *ee*% than their parent catalysts.

The enzyme *Candida cylindracea* (CCL) and catalyst **e**, lipozyme and catalyst **f** were found to behave identically. However, *Porcine pancreatin* (PPL) was found to show selectivity towards the other isomer. The results with PPL* were found to be the best. Better result was anticipated for PPL* as the conditions selected were as preferred by enzyme, known in literature⁷, for these types of reactions. The enzymes amno A and amno P did not show any enantioselectivity.

It is observed from the *ee*% values (Table 1) that the enantioselectivity capability of CMLM complexes is improved to the extent of five times with increase of steric bulk. On further modification of the catalyst (by introduction of *N*-benzoyl group) the catalyst shows further improvement of around

TABLE 1—VALUES OF ee% FOR PRODUCT (1*) OBTAINED BY USING CMLM COMPLEXES AND ENZYMES AS CATALYSTS

Complex .	ee%	Isomer
a	7	R
b	28	R
c	29	R
d	33	R
e	14	R
f	44	R
Enzyme		
Amno p	0	
Amno A	0	
PPL	5	S
CCL	17	R
Lipozyme	43	R
PPL ^a	66	S

*All the results are for 10% conversion to 1. ^aEnzyme preferred organic solvent

two times. Fig. 1 gives the idea about the variation of ee% of the product (1) at different percentage conversions for the reaction with different catalysts.

Experimental

Chiral mixed ligand metal (CMLM) complexes of the type MLL', where M = Co^{II}, HL = isonitrosoacetophenone (HINAP); HL' = chiral (L) amino acids (MLL' = a, b, c, d, e and f when HL' = alanine, leucine, valine, phenylalanine, *N*-benzoylalanine and *N*-benzoylphenylalanine respectively) were synthesised. The complexes were prepared by refluxing cobalt(II) chloride, HINAP and solution of sodium salt of chiral amino acids in equimolar ratio in ethanol for 3–4 h. The complexes were characterised by elemental analysis, electronic, ir and nmr spectra.

Fig 1 Plots of % conversion vs %ee : (•) PPL*, (O) Cat f, lipozyme, (□) cat. d, (▲) Cat. e, CCL and (Δ) cat a, PPL

Transesterification : The substrate (diacetate of 1) (300 mg, 0.8 mM) was stirred with catalyst (100 mg) in methanol (5 ml) acting as nucleophile as well as solvent. The reactions were monitored by tlc and hplc. The enzyme-catalysed reactions were stopped by filtration, whereas for CMLM complex catalysed reactions, the solutions were first evaporated to dryness in vacuum and then filtered through silica in dichloromethane. The extent of conversion and ee% were quantitatively determined by hplc using chiral Pirkle DNPG column. The elution was done with solvent hexane-isopropanol (95 : 5) with a flow rate of 1 ml min⁻¹. The absorbance at 254 nm was monitored. the retention times of the diacetate, monoacetate, diol (S), diol (R) were 10.90, 15.21, 18.21 and 23.90 min respectively.

For reaction with lipase PPL*, the solvent used was toluene (5 ml), and substrate (300 mg) to n-butanol (0.3 ml nucleophile) molar ratio was 1 : 4 and the enzyme quantity was identical (100 mg) as in other reaction.

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